

Table 4

Properties and composition of oil and condensate (horizontal average)

Horizon	Perforation interval (m)	D ²⁰ ₄	T _{sol} C ⁰	Viscosity, sPz	
				20 C ⁰	50 C ⁰
oil					
NK-9	3670-3680	0,9103	+36	non - fluid	63,8
condensate					
NK -7d	3512-3624	0,7943	-3	1,9	-
NK -8	3616-3625	0,7903	+3	1,8	-

Table 5

Properties and composition of oil and condensate (horizontal average)

Horizon	Perforation interval (m)	End of boiling %, up to temperature C ⁰					
		100	150	200	250	300	exit
oil							
NK -9	3670-3680	-	4	7	10	16	-
condensate							
NK -7d	3512-3624	12	29	42	56	74	90
NK -8	3616-3625	9	27	42	57	76	93

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NEUTRAL GROUNDING MODE IN THE 6–35 kV NETWORK THROUGH AN ARCING REACTOR AND ORGANIZATION OF RELAY PROTECTION AGAINST SINGLE-PHASE GROUND FAULTS

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Abstract

The choice of the neutral grounding mode in the 6–35 kV network (or, in other words, the method of neutral grounding) is an extremely important issue in the design and operation. In this article, one of the neutral grounding modes in 6-35kV networks is considered - through an arcing reactor. The choice of the neutral grounding mode in 6–35 kV networks is an extremely important issue in the operation and design of the network.

The use of modern neutral grounding equipment in 6–35 kV networks (arc-quenching reactors with low-voltage shunt resistors and high-voltage neutral grounding resistors) can significantly improve the reliability of networks, automate the search for a damaged feeder and reduce accidents in case of single-phase ground faults.

Keywords: neutral grounding, arcing reactor, shunt resistor, arc surges

The neutral grounding mode in the 6–35 kV network determines:

- current in the place of damage and overvoltage on undamaged phases in case of single-phase circuit;
- scheme for constructing relay protection against earth faults;

- electrical equipment insulation level;
- uninterrupted power supply;
- allowable resistance of the substation ground loop;
- safety of personnel and electrical equipment during single-phase faults.

Thus, it is obvious that the neutral grounding mode in the 6–35 kV network affects a significant number of technical solutions that are implemented in a particular network.

In medium voltage networks (with a rated voltage of up to 69 kV according to foreign classification), 4 neutral grounding modes are used (Pic. 1)

Pic.1. Neutral grounding modes for medium voltage networks

That is, all over the world in medium voltage networks (up to 69 kV), in contrast to high voltage networks (110 kV and above), four possible options for grounding the neutral point of the network are used:

- insulated (ungrounded);
- grounded through an arcing reactor;
- grounded through a resistor (low or high resistance);
- deafly grounded.

In addition to these four neutral grounding modes, a combination (parallel connection) of an arcing reactor and a resistor is also used in the world. For example, such a

combination is found in German 20 kV overhead networks, where an arcing reactor provides extinguishing of short-term single-phase insulation flashes to earth, and a low-resistance resistor is connected to the neutral of the network in parallel with the reactor only for a short time with a special single-phase power switch.

The resistor in such a circuit serves to selectively determine the feeder with a stable single-phase earth fault. If you look at the world practice of operating medium voltage networks (see table 1), you can clearly see that neutral grounding through a resistor or an arcing reactor is most often used.

Table 1.

Neutral grounding mode in medium voltage networks 3–69 kV in various countries of the world

Country	Method of grounding the neutral			
	Isolated	Grounded through reactor	Grounded through resistor	Blind grounding
Russia	+	+		
Australia			+	+
Canada			+	+
USA			+	+
Spain		+	+	+
Portugal			+	
France		+	+	
Japan			+	
Germany		+	+	
Austria		+	+	
Belgium			+	
Great Britain			+	+
Switzerland		+	+	
Finland	+	+	+	
Italy		+	+	
Czech		+	+	

Consider one of the neutral grounding modes in 6–35kV networks through an arcing reactor. Picture 2 shows a typical two-transformer substation with neutral on the 6–10 kV side grounded through the arc reactor.

In this mode, a neutral output transformer (with a Y-0/D or Z-0 winding connection) and an arc quenching reactor are connected to the 6–10 kV bus section through a specially dedicated cell.

Pic. 2 Step-down substation with neutral on the 6-10 kV side grounded through the arcing reactor

In case of a single-phase earth fault in the network, the arcing reactor creates an inductive current component equal to the capacitive one at the fault site. In this case, the total current at the fault site becomes almost zero, and the first single-phase ground fault that occurs in the network cannot be turned off.

In medium voltage networks of 3–69 kV in European countries (Germany, Czech Republic, Switzerland, Austria, France, Italy, Romania, Poland, Finland, Sweden, etc.), neutral grounding through an arcing reactor with a low-voltage shunt resistor is widely used (Pic. 2). A low-voltage shunt resistor with a voltage of 500 V is connected through a special contactor to the secondary power winding of 500 V of the arcing reactor. This technical solution has the following advantages:

- no need to immediately disconnect a single-phase earth fault and, accordingly, the consumer;
- low residual current at the point of damage (no more than 1–2 A);
- self-liquidation of single-phase short circuits (especially on overhead lines);
- the possibility of organizing selective automatic relay protection against single-phase earth faults.

In existing 6–35 kV networks with neutral grounding through arcing reactors of the old design with manual control and reactors with magnetization, but without a shunt resistor, there is a problem of organizing selective protection against single-phase earth faults. Both simple overcurrent earth-fault protections (ANSI code 51G) and directional protections (ANSI code 67N) cannot be used on these networks.

The first one is due to the fact that the arcing reactor compensates for the single-phase fault current (current $3I_0$) in the damaged connection almost to zero. The second ones are due to the coincidence of the direction of the current $3I_0$ in the damaged and undamaged feeders in direction. In the damaged feeder, in the direction “from the busbars”, an inductive current $3I_0$ flows in magnitude equal to the feeder’s own capacitive current,

and in undamaged feeders, own capacitive currents flow in the direction “towards the busbars”.

The mode of grounding the neutral through an arcing reactor with a shunt low-voltage resistor connected to the secondary power winding with a voltage of 500 V makes it possible to implement selective earth fault protection using both simple current protections (ANSI code 51G) and more complex directional protections in the direction of current $3I_0$ (ANSI code 67N) or zero-sequence active power (“wattmetric”, ANSI code 32). As a rule, earth fault protections in this case act on the signal (the current at the fault is small and its immediate disconnection is not required).

In the presence of a shunt low-voltage (500 V) resistor, the logic for using arc-quenching reactors is as follows. Until a single-phase fault occurs, the arcing reactor is tuned to resonance, and the shunt resistor is turned off. In the initial stage of closing, the arc is usually unstable and re-ignitions and extinctions occur. In this case, the reactor acts as an arc extinguishing device, and allows you not to turn off the damaged feeder.

In the event that the circuit has become stable, with a certain time delay set in the

REG-DPA regulator of the reactor, a shunt resistor is connected (for a period of 1 to 3 seconds). The reactor’s REG-DPA digital regulator commands the 500 V shunt resistor contactor to be turned on, which is connected to the reactor’s 500 V secondary power winding.

Connecting a shunt resistor for 1–3 seconds creates an active current $3I_0$ only in the damaged feeder, the value of which is determined by the resistance of the resistor and can be from 5 to 50 A. This current is sufficient for the selective operation of even conventional earth fault current protection of a damaged connection.

In normal mode, the low-voltage shunt resistor SR of the arcing reactor is disabled and does not affect the accuracy of the compensation setting. The resistor is connected only for the time required for the operation of the earth fault protection (1–3 sec). The thermal resistance of the resistor is typically 6 to 60 seconds.

The use of modern neutral grounding equipment in 6–35 kV networks (arcing reactors with low-voltage shunt resistors and high-voltage neutral grounding resistors) can significantly improve the reliability of networks, automate the search for a damaged feeder and reduce accidents in case of single-phase ground faults.

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